

AN ASSESSMENT OF EDUCATIONAL FACILITIES IN OZORO AND ITS ENVIRONS

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Abstract

The availability and adequacy of educational facilities are pivotal to the achievement of educational goals, aims and objectives through meeting the physical and psychological needs of both learners and teaching staff. Therefore, this article investigated the educational facilities in Ozoro as well as those in its environs. The article employed observational research, to assess the state of educational facilities, it also collected primary and secondary data from the education ministry in Isoko North Local Government Area, where Ozoro is located. The findings were presented with tables and bar charts. The findings reveal that there are limited public educational facilities in the area, as there are more private schools than public ones. The authors also discovered a low number of support or non-teaching staff, to the extent that the communities have to employ and pay their own set of teachers, to argument those employed by the government. However, there is a low teacher-pupil/student ratio, with the exception of public primary schools. Therefore, the article recommended that government should overhaul the educational facilities in the area, physical infrastructure of public primary and secondary schools should also be renovated, while new ones should be provided.

Keywords: Educational Facilities, Ozoro, Primary Schools, Secondary Schools, Teachers, Private and Public Schools, and Delta State.

1. Introduction

An educational facility is a building or collection of buildings with all inbuilt facilities that are purposely constructed and use for educational activities. Okosun et al., (2020) defined educational facilities as the physical, human and material resources utilized in the effective management of educational institutions. Nkem & Peretomode (2025) opined that educational facilities are numerous and include well-furnished classrooms/lecture halls; well stocked libraries; administrative offices; cafeterias; science laboratories; clean conveniences (toilets); computer resource rooms; staff residence; assembly halls; workshops; portable water; sporting facilities; playground and many others. In Nigeria, educational standard and quality has been falling over the years and decades unabated, due to inadequacy of educational facilities and decay of the available ones (Asiyai 2012; Islam & Salma, 2016; Okosun et al., 2020 and Iloh, et al., 2020). This decay may be attributed to the nonchalant attitude of successive governments in meeting the demands of schools, and also occasioned by the geometric population increase experienced all over the country.

A plethora of research (Amanchukwu & Ololube, 2015; Iloh et al., 2020; Emordi, 2021; Teixeira et al., 2017; Yangambi, 2023; and Peretomode & Obed-Chukwuka, 2024) have established a strong link between the provision of quality educational facilities and learners academic attainment and attitude towards schooling. Therefore, availability of educational facilities for the educational development of its citizens should be a top priority of a responsible government at any level (Samuel Group, 2023; Ayyubi & Abdullah, 2024; Yuniarti et al 2023; Adriansah et al., 2025). This is because the availability and adequacy of educational facilities are pivotal to the achievement of educational goals, aims and objectives through meeting the physical and psychological needs of both learners and teaching staff (Amanchukwu & Ololobe, 2015; Adeleke & Adeleke 2024; and Iloh, et al., 2020). Bearing these in mind, the researchers assessed the availability and sufficiency of educational facilities in Ozoro located in Isoko North Local Government Area in Delta State, Nigeria.

2. Method

The research procedure utilized in this study was observational research, the researchers also embarked on the collection of data using primary and secondary methods. The population of the study involved the entire educational institutions in Ozoro metropolis and its environs, from tertiary, secondary to primary educational institutions. The population also included private schools, hence complete enumeration sampling was applied. Data analysis was done with the aid of tables, bar charts and maps.

3. Findings

Ozoro is located in Isoko North Local Government Area (LGA) of Delta State in Nigeria (See Figures 1 & 2). Its environs include Owhelegbo and Otor-owhe in the west; Ellu in the North and Arhade in the North East (See Figure 1). It was observed that educational facilities are geographically spread across Ozoro and environs, beginning from the Early Childhood Education (ECE) commonly known as nursery/kindergarten school to basic/primary, secondary and post-secondary (tertiary) educational institutions. This article concerned itself with an assessment of educational facilities in the area especially private (government approved) and public, primary and secondary schools in the Ozoro and its adjoining areas

Observations of the researchers who went around Ozoro and its environs revealed that educational facilities in public primary and secondary schools of Ozoro town are dilapidated and overstressed. Most of the buildings have broken roofs, broken windows, broken doors, broken floors and broken wall. Similarly, the furniture are in a state of neglect and ruins. For instance, out of 434 classrooms in the area only 230 are good, the good ones are mainly those in private schools. While out of a total of 7682 desks, only 5894 are in good order. Similarly, more than 90% of the public schools have no access to electricity supply. Library facilities are scarce in almost all the public schools in Ozoro and environs, in schools where available, they are mostly un-kept, dirty, and not stocked with books. The libraries in few private schools visited are equally sub-standard (Source: Authors Field Work). This poor availability of educational facilities in Ozoro schools if left unattended to will definitely jettison the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals in the area (Atubi, 2019).

Figure 1: Map of Ozoro Showing Educational Facilities

Source: Researcher's Fieldwork

Figure 2: Map of Isoko North LGA, Showing the Educational Facilities in Ozoro Environs.

Source: Researcher’s Fieldwork

Tertiary Education

Ozoro is home to one university, Southern Delta University (SDU) formerly called Delta State University of Science and Technology (DELSUST) located in the northern part of the town. The university is owned and operated by the Delta State Government and established from the defunct Delta State Polytechnic Ozoro, it was officially accredited and recognized to start operation by the National University Commission in February, 2021. On inception, it has a student enrollment population of One Thousand Nine Hundred and Eighty (1980) and a staff strength of Seven Hundred and Eighty two (782). It has seven (7) faculties, with forty-five (45) academic programmes, the faculties are: Agriculture, Earth Sciences, Engineering, Environmental, Sciences, Information Technology and Management Technology Science

Polytechnics/Monotechnics/Vocational Centers

Ozoro have no polytechnic at present, as the defunct Delta State Polytechnic Ozoro has been converted to the Delta State University of Science and Technology (DELSUST). However the town has the following Monotechnics and vocational centers;

1. National Teachers, Institute, Ozoro.
2. Catholic Diocese of Warri Music Academy (private).
3. Film and Broadcast Academy (FABA) (private).

Source: www.wikiwand.com/en/ozoro

Primary and Secondary Educational Institutions in Ozoro and Environs

Ozoro and environs can be said to boast of a good number of primary/basic and secondary schools, see tables 1 -4:

Table 1: Educational Facilities of Public Primary Schools in Ozoro and Environs

s/no	Name of School	Total No of Pupils	Number of Teachers		Non-Teaching Staff	Teacher Pupil Ratio
			Permanent & N-Power Teachers	Community Teachers		
1.	Amawhe P/S, Ozoro	290	14	Nil	Nil	1:26
2.	Arhade P/S, Arhade	326	6	4	Nil	1:23
3.	Azabga P/S, Otor-Owhe	253	9	Nil	Nil	1:28
4.	Bovi P/S, Ozoro	349	16	Nil	2	1:22
5.	Egware P/S, Ozoro	248	9	1	4	1:23
6.	Ekwerigbe P/S, Ozoro	441	12	Nil	Nil	1:37

7.	Ellu P/S, Ellu	221	8	Nil	1	1:28
8.	Eni P/S Ellu	162	5	2	1	1:32
9.	Olordo P/S, Ozoro	465	13	1	2	1:36
10.	Orokpokpo P/S, Owhelogbo	428	6	4	Nil	1:43
11.	Ovie P/S, Ellu	68	6	Nil	Nil	1:11
12.	Ovo P/S, Otor-owhe	133	6	Nil	Nil	1:22
13.	Owhelogbo P/S, Owhelogbo	144	6	Nil	4	1:24
14.	Special Center Education, Ozoro	23	6	3	Nil	1:8
15.	Uruogbe P/S, Owhelogbo	426	7	Nil	Nil	1:23
	Total-15 P/Schools	3344	129	15	14	1:63

Source: Ministry of Basic and Secondary Education, Isoko North Local Government Area (2025).

Table 1, presents the number of public primary schools in the study area, Ozoro and environs have a total of 15 public primary schools as at 2025. The table also reveal a total of 3344 pupils in those primary schools, with about 129 permanent/n-power teachers; 15 community paid teachers; 14 non-teaching staff; and an overall teacher pupil ratio of 1:63. This ratio is quite high, it implies that there is a need for more teachers to be engaged in those public primary schools. The number of non-teaching staff is also very few, when compared to the total number of pupils in these schools.

Table 2: Educational Facilities of Government Approved Private Primary Schools in Ozoro and Environs.

s/no	Name of School	Total No of Pupils	Number of Teachers		Non-Teaching Staff	Teacher Pupil Ratio
			Permanent and N-Power Teachers	Community Teachers		
1.	Anglican PS, Ozoro	179	12	Nil	4	1:15
2.	Anointed P/S, Otor-owhe	151	13	Nil	2	1:11
3.	C.E.M Total Child, Ozoro	198	15	Nil	3	1:13
4.	Christ Guide P/S Ozoro	227	10	Nil	4	1:23
5.	Covenant Kings and Queen P/S, Owhelogbo	274	9	Nil	2	1:30
6.	De-Achievers P/S, Ozoro	127	9	Nil	3	1:14
7.	DELSUST D/P/S, Ozoro	163	21	Nil	4	1:8
8.	Ewoma P/S, Owhelogbo	163	6	Nil	2	1:27
9.	Final Touch INT'L P/S, Ozoro	343	21	Nil	7	1:16
10.	Focus P/S, Otor-owhe	143	9	Nil	1	1:16
11.	Glory P/S, Ozoro	166	11	Nil	1	1:15
12.	Goodly Heritage M/P/S, Owhelogbo	66	8	Nil	Nil	1:8
13.	Gospel P/S, Ozoro	61	6	Nil	1	1:10
14.	Grace Guide P/S, Otor-owhe.	138	8	Nil	1	1:17
15.	Heroes Dynamic G/P/S. Ozoro	198	8	Nil	1	1:25
16.	Hope Foundation P/S, Ozoro	90	8	Nil	1	1:11
17.	JOEVILLE P/S, Owhelogbo	58	8	Nil	Nil	1:7
18.	Kingdom Heritage M/P/S Ozoro	113	10	Nil	1	1:11
19.	Meeco P/S, Ozoro	26	5	Nil	Nil	1:5
20.	Missionary Prayer Band P/S, Ozoro	156	7	Nil	3	1:22
21.	Omega P/S, Ozoro	47	5	Nil	Nil	1:9
22.	Opute, Model P/S, Ozoro	92	8	Nil	3	1:12

23.	Parapet P/S, Ozoro	245	20	Nil	4	1:12
24.	Royal Foundation P/S, Ozoro	357	10	Nil	6	1:36
25.	Sacred Heart P/S, Ozoro	380	35	Nil	14	1:11
26.	Spring child Noble Crest, P/S, Ozoro	310	10	Nil	3	1:31
27.	St Paul P/S, Ozoro	398	19	Nil	6	1:21
28.	Total Child P/S, Ozoro	133	6	Nil	1	1:22
29.	Vision INT'L P/S, Ozoro	129	6	Nil	3	1:22
30.	Zoelight INT'L P/S, Ozoro	37	5	Nil	2	1:18
	Total-30 Private P/Schools	5168	328	Nil	84	1:15

Source: Ministry of Basic and Secondary Education, Isoko North Local Government Area (2025).

Data on government approved private primary schools is presented in Table 2, from the table, it can be observed that the total number of private primary schools is 30, this number is far higher than the number of public primary schools run by the Isoko North Local Government Area. Similarly, the total number of pupils in private primary schools in the study area of 5168 is a huge gap from the 3344 in public or government owned primary schools. Permanent teachers in the schools are 328 as compared to 129 that are in public primary schools, as expected there are no community teachers in private primary schools, because they are fully run by private individuals and organizations. There are 84 non-teaching staff versus only 14 in the public schools. A teacher ratio of 1:15 was recorded, this is quite low and commendable.

Table 3: Educational Facilities of Public Secondary Schools in Ozoro and Environs

s/no	Name of School	Total No of Pupils	Number of Teachers		Non-Teaching Staff	Teacher Pupil Ratio
			Permanent and N-Power Teachers	Community Paid Teachers		
1.	Alaka G/S, Ozoro	680	35	Nil	24	1:19
2.	Aradhe G/ S, Aradhe	275	19	2	Nil	1:10
3.	Emo-Eni G/S, Ellu	343	26	Nil	6	1:13
4.	Government S/S,Owhelogbo	462	18	2	4	1:23
5.	Igbonine G/S, Ozoro.	324	37	Nil	12	1:9
6.	Illuelogbo G/S, Owhelogbo	445	25	Nil	12	1:18
7.	I.C.E.,Ozoro	304	25	1	6	1:13
8.	Owhe G/S, Otor-Owhe	537	34	3	5	1:15
	Total-8 S/Schools	3370	215	8	69	1:15

Source: Ministry of Basic and Secondary Education, Isoko North Local Government Area (2025).

The results shown in Table 3, reflected the lack of public secondary schools in the whole of Ozoro and its environs, only eight (8) schools are built in the area. While the total number of secondary school students stood at 3370, with 215 permanent and n-power teachers. The community also engaged the services of eight teachers, whom they pay from the community purse, while non-teaching staff are 69. Finally a teacher ratio of 1:15 was reported. This suggest that they are more than enough teachers in the few schools, perhaps the small number of schools lead to the concentration of teachers in them.

s/no	Name of School	Total No of Pupils	Number of Teachers		Non-Teaching Staff	Teacher Pupil Ratio
			Permanent and N-Power Teachers	Community Teachers		
1.	African United G/S, Owhelogbo	235	8	Nil	3	1:18
2.	Anglican Girls G/S, Ozoro	201	20	Nil	11	1:10
3.	Covenant Kings and Queens, Owhelogbo	149	14	Nil	2	1:11
4.	DELSUST D/S/S, Ozoro	281	25	Nil	2	1:11
5.	De-Wis S/S, Ozoro	110	7	Nil	3	1:16

6.	Final Touch INT'L. S/S. Ozoro	638	NA	Nil	NA	NA
7.	Heroes Dynamic S/S, Ozoro	191	16	Nil	4	1:12
8.	Hope Foundation S/S,Ozoro.	299	13	Nil	4	1:23
9.	Joeville S/S, Owhelogbo	86	10	Nil	3	1:9
10.	Mega Touch S/S, Owhelogbo	60	11	Nil	2	1:5
11.	Missionary Prayer Band, S/S, Ozoro	226	9	Nil	1	1:25
12.	Notre Dame College, Ozoro	358	27	Nil	18	1:13
13.	Opute Memorial G/S, Ozoro	127	13	Nil	0	1:10
14.	Parapet S/S,Ozoro	390	30	Nil	4	1:13
15.	Royal Foundation Academy, Ozoro	536	22	Nil	12	1:24
16.	Spring Child Noblecrest, Ozoro	400	25	Nil	4	1:16
17.	St. Joseph College Ozoro	278	23	Nil	9	1:12
18.	St. Paul S/S, Ozoro.	382	18	Nil	2	1:21
19.	Vision Int. School, Ozoro	207	12	Nil	3	1:16
	Total-19 Private/S/Schools	5154	301	Nil	84	1:16

Table 4: Educational Facilities of Government Approved Private Secondary Schools in Ozoro and Environs

Source: Ministry of Basic and Secondary Education, Isoko North Local Government Area (2025).

In Table 4, the researchers gave a detailed information on the private secondary schools located in Ozoro and its environs. The results clearly suggest that the number of privately owned and run secondary school far outnumbered those built by the government, as there are 19 private secondary schools as against 8 public secondary schools in the study area. In addition there are 5154 students in private secondary schools, against 3370 in public ones. The table also shows that 301 teachers are employed in the private secondary schools, while the public ones have 215, eight community teachers with none in the private schools, and 84 nonteaching staff as compared to 69 in the public schools. Finally, the teacher student ratio in both private and public secondary schools are almost the same with 1:16 in private schools as against 1:15 in public secondary schools.

Fig: 3: A Chart showing private, public primary and secondary schools in Ozoro and environs (Authors Field Work).

4. Discussion

The findings from this observational research, showed that the number of public primary schools in Ozoro and environs, especially public ones are minimal, when compared to those of private primary schools. This suggests that the public primary schools will be crowded with fewer facilities for the pupils, the implication is that there is need for the provision of more public secondary schools in the area. On the other hand, there are also a very small number of government owned secondary schools, viz a viz the privately owned secondary schools in the area. In a similar scenario, the privately run schools are better furnished and equipped with better educational

facilities such as e-libraries, beautiful classrooms, desks, neat environment, well ventilated classrooms and more. This observation, calls for action both the local and state government, intervention should be holistic and all embracing, and this is in line with Peretomode & Obed-Chukwuka (2024) and Emordi (2021). These studies canvassed for better educational facilities to be provided in both private and specially public schools.

The findings presented also give an impression of low numbers of support staff/non-teaching staff, especially in public primary and secondary schools. In addition, it could be observed that the communities have paid community teachers in some schools, this depicts inadequate teachers to man the classes or subjects. However, the pupil teacher or student teacher ratio seems to be very encouraging as they are far below the United Nations benchmark of 1:40, except in Uruogbe primary school in Owhelogbo where the ratio was 1:61. This might be attributed to the rural nature of the surrounding communities, as only Ozoro main metropolis can be regarded as an urban center. Therefore, Isoko North LGA and Delta state government should ensure the overhauling of educational facilities across all public primary and secondary schools.

This overhauling of educational facilities should be extended to the privately owned schools as they form majority of schools in the area investigated. There should also be proper monitoring by the relevant regulatory agencies in the educational sector, this will ensure strict compliance in the provision of educational facilities in schools. Private individuals and groups, well-meaning indigenes, religious organizations, and the Ozoro community as a whole should rise up to the occasion by making adequate educational facilities such as well-furnished classrooms/lecture halls; well stocked libraries; administrative offices; cafeterias; science laboratories; clean conveniences (toilets); computer resource rooms; staff residence; assembly halls; workshops; portable water; sporting facilities and playgrounds available in the schools in the area. These implications of the findings are in tandem with, Nkem & Peretomode (2025); Yangambi (2023); and Okosun et al., (2020).

The multiplying effect of quality education can never be over emphasized, hence, the local educational authority in the LGA, should ensure that school enrollment be made commensurate to the available facilities on ground. Maintenance culture of school plant and facilities should be developed, encouraged and inculcated in staff, pupils and students as applicable. Funds should be disbursed from other agencies like the Delta State Oil Producing and Development Commission (DESOPADEC), because Ozoro is a part of this commission as an oil producing community. The quality of educational facilities repair or provision should be of high quality and standard to achieve durability and stand the test of time.

5. Conclusions

The article established that educational facilities are paramount to quality education at all levels, therefore, the government of Delta State and Isoko North LGA should make tenacious efforts in maintaining the existing educational facilities, while providing new ones in schools of Ozoro and environs. Nevertheless, evidence on ground gave an impression of underfunding and provision of educational facilities, this gross inadequacy can negatively impact growth in school enrollment, students' academic performance and human capital development in Ozoro and environs. The dilapidating state of both physical and human educational facilities on ground, especially in government owned schools need to be addressed urgently. Finally, it was observed and concluded that majority of schools in the area are private ones, therefore, there is an urgent need for the provision of more government owned schools with the state of the art educational facilities.

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